

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Kurbanov Nematilla

**THE INTERACTION BETWEEN THE PRODUCT TO BE GROUND AND
THE GRINDING BLADE IN THE GRINDING CHAMBER**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

2023/IYUN

★★★★★
HONORED
MENTION
★★★★★

YOUR
SEAL